

THIOKETONIC ESTERS. PART V.

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Synthesis of some unpolymerised β -thioketonic esters has been achieved. Some reactions characteristic to these compounds comparable with those of the corresponding oxygen analogues have been studied. The structures of sodiothioketonic esters has also been confirmed conclusively.

The formation of unpolymerised sulphur analogues from the reaction of hydrogen sulphide with ketonic compounds *e.g.* β -ketonic esters, possessing marked tendency of enolisation has been suggested in a previous communication (Mitra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 71). The present investigation deals mainly with the general applicability of the reaction and a study of the methylene group activated by the thiocarbonyl group thus introduced.

Diethyl thioacetylmalonate has been synthesised from the interaction of hydrogen sulphide and the corresponding oxygen analogue. Its constitution has been established by the synthesis of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-carbethoxy-5-ketopyrazolone (I) from the reaction of the thioketo-ester with phenylhydrazine.

Ethyl methylthioacetoacetate (Ia) in unpolymerised state, together with another material, has been isolated from the reaction of hydrogen sulphide with ethyl methylacetoacetate. The latter compound does not possess any thiol or thioketonic group. Structure (II) has been suggested for it.

Evidently the compound was formed through oxidation of two molecules of the thioketo-ester in thiol phase.

Thus it appears conclusive that the sodio derivative of β -thioketonic esters mainly exists in $\text{>C-S}'\text{Na}$ phase unlike β -ketonic esters and a simple replacement of sodium with alkyl group explains the formation of S-ethers. If the addition of sodio derivative depend upon the tendency of saturation of the unsaturated system, then the failure of ethylene derivatives to form any additive products is obvious. The influence of the unsaturated system in ethyl cinnamate on the sodium atom in the mercaptide phase of the thio-ester is of the order of what it (sodium) is already under, due to the presence of a double bond in the sodio derivative itself and hence is not sufficient to effect any addition. Thus the capability of β -ketonic esters to react with the unsaturated compounds of the ethylene series and the formation of C-ethers on alkylation clearly prove the structure of their sodio-derivative as $\text{>CH}'\text{Na}$.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl Thioacetylmalonate.—Diethyl acetylmalonate (15 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (50 c.c.) saturated with dry hydrogen chloride. Hydrogen sulphide was passed through the solution (24 hours at 15°). The mixture was poured over ice and extracted with benzene (200 c.c.). The benzene solution was washed with sodium carbonate, dried and distilled at 120° / 4 mm. (Found : C, 49.6 ; H, 6.6 ; S, 14.3. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4\text{S}$ requires C, 49.5 ; H, 6.4 ; S, 14.6 per cent).

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-carbethoxy-5-ketopyrazolone.—Diethyl thioacetyl-

malonate (4 g.) was mixed with phenylhydrazine (2 mol. per 1 mol. of ester). When the evolution of hydrogen sulphide moderated, the mixture was heated at 100° for 8 hours. The product after washing with ether furnished colourless needles from acetic acid, m.p. 121-22°. It was identified in the usual manner. It gave a violet colouration with ferric chloride.

Ethyl Methylthioacetoacetate.—Hydrogen sulphide was passed (18 hours) through a solution of ethyl methylacetoacetate (100 g.) dissolved in alcohol (200 c.c.) saturated with dry hydrogen chloride. The oil which separated on pouring the mixture over ice was extracted with benzene. The fraction, b.p. 78°-104°/10 mm. was collected from the benzene solution. This was dissolved in ethyl alcohol (100 c.c.) and while the solution was stirred, freshly precipitated lead oxide was slowly added. The yellow lead salt was collected and washed with alcohol. The mercaptide was decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid and the liberated ester was extracted with benzene (500 c.c.). The fraction, b.p. 95°/10 mm. was isolated from the benzene solution. (Found : C, 52·2 ; H, 7·6 ; S, 19·5. $C_7H_{12}O_2S$ requires C, 52·5 ; H, 7·5 ; S, 20·0 per cent).

Ethyl isoButylthioacetoacetate.—Hydrogen sulphide was passed (24 hours) through a solution of ethyl isobutylacetoacetate (25 g.) in ethyl alcohol (100 c.c.) saturated with dry hydrogen chloride. The mixture was extracted, purified in the usual manner as stated above and the ester was isolated as an oil, b.p. 122°/5 mm. (Found : C, 59·2 ; H, 9·1 ; S, 15·3. $C_{12}H_{18}O_2S$ requires C, 59·4 ; H, 8·9 ; S, 15·8 per cent). Freshly distilled thioketonic esters are rose-red liquids possessing sweetish smell. The colour deepens with rise of temperature. Phenylhydrazine reacts with them at the room temperature (15°) with liberation of hydrogen sulphide. Alcoholic ferric chloride gives a violet colouration and alcoholic iodine is rapidly decolourised. They form coloured lead salt and react with metallic sodium vigorously with evolution of hydrogen.

Ethyl β -Methylmercapto- α -methylcrotonate.—Ethyl methylthioacetoacetate (8 g.) was added to ethyl alcohol (50 c.c.) containing sodium (1 g.). Methyl sulphate (6 g.) was next added to the mixture which was boiled under reflux (4 hours). The product on treatment with excess of water was extracted with benzene. The fraction, b.p. 225°/750 mm. was collected from the benzene solution. (Found : C, 54·9 ; H, 8·2 ; S, 18·2. $C_8H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 55·1 ; H, 8·0 ; S, 18·3 per cent).

Ethyl β -Methylmercapto- α -methylcrotonate (5 g.) was boiled with aqueous hydrochloric acid (d 1·19, 25 c.c. diluted with 25 c.c. of water). The liberated gases were passed through washers containing alcoholic iodine and baryta. Methyl disulphide was identified in the iodine solution.

The liberation of methylmercaptan confirms the S-ether structure of the alkylated products.

Ethyl β -Ethylmercapto- α -methylcrotonate.—Ethyl methylthioacetate (13 g.) was added to emulsified sodium (2 g.), suspended in dry benzene (50 c.c.). After keeping the mixture at the room temperature (15°) for 2 hours, ethyl iodide (16 g.) was added and the mixture boiled under reflux (6 hours). The thio-ether was isolated as an oil, b.p. 220°/7 mm. (Found: C, 57.0; H, 8.6. $C_9H_{16}O_2S$ requires C, 57.4; H, 8.5 per cent).

Ethyl β -Methylcarbethoxymercapto- α -methylcrotonate.—Ethyl monochloroacetate (13 g.) was added to sodio derivative of ethyl methylthioacetate (ester, 18 g.; sodium, 3 g.) in benzene suspension and the mixture was boiled under reflux (5 hours). The thio-ether was isolated as an oil, b.p. 160°/6 mm. (Found: C, 53.3; H, 7.5. $C_{11}H_{18}O_4S$ requires C, 53.6; H, 7.3 per cent).

Diethyl Methylthioacetate (II).—Hydrogen sulphide was passed (12 hours) through a solution of ethyl methylacetate (20 g.), dissolved in alcohol (100 c.c.) saturated with hydrogen chloride. The mixture was left at the room temperature (15°) for 3 days, poured over ice and extracted with benzene. After the removal of the low boiling fraction, mainly consisting of unpolymerised ethyl methylthioacetate and its unreacted oxygen analogue, a fraction, b.p. 180°/6 mm., was collected. The same product was isolated by oxidation of unpolymerised ethyl methylthioacetate with alcoholic iodine. (Found: C, 52.6; H, 7.1; S, 20.0. $C_{14}H_{22}O_4S_2$ requires C, 52.8; H, 6.9; S, 20.1 per cent).

Ethyl β -Methylmercapto-glutaconate.—Dimethyl sulphate (6 g.) was added to sodio derivative of ethyl thioacetonedicarboxylate (ester, 20 g.; sodium, 2.1 g.) and the mixture was boiled (4 hours). The thio-ether was isolated as an oil, b.p. 135°/6 mm. (Found: C, 51.6; H, 6.8; S, 14.0. $C_{10}H_{16}O_4S$ requires C, 51.7; H, 6.8; S, 13.7 per cent).

Ethyl β -Acetylmercapto-glutaconate.—A mixture of ethyl thioacetonedicarboxylate (20 g.) and acetic anhydride (50 c.c.) containing pyridine (1 c.c.) was boiled under reflux (4 hours). The mixture was poured into ice and extracted with ether. The fraction, b.p. 150°/9 mm., was isolated from the ethereal extract. (Found: C, 50.4; H, 6.1. $C_{11}H_{16}O_5S$ requires C, 50.7; H, 6.1 per cent).

Ethyl β -Methylcarbethoxymercapto-glutaconate.—Ethyl monochloroacetate (12 g.) was added to sodio ethyl thioacetonedicarboxylate (ester, 19 g., sodium, 2 g.) in ethyl alcohol (40 c.c.) and the mixture was boiled. The compound was obtained as an oil, b.p. 170°/6 mm. (Found: C, 51.2; H, 6.8; S, 10.2. $C_{16}H_{26}O_6S$ requires C, 51.3; H, 6.6; S, 10.5 per cent).

Action of n-Butylmagnesium Iodide on Ethyl Thioacetondicarboxylate.—Ethyl thioacetonedicarboxylate (5 g.) was added to *n*-butylmagnesium iodide (Mg, 1 g.; butyl iodide, 6 g.) in ether solution. The pasty yellow mass, which separated, was washed several times with ether. The material on treatment with aqueous hydrochloric acid liberated ethyl thioacetonedicarboxylate unchanged. During the addition of ethyl thioacetonedicarboxylate to butylmagnesium halide, a copious evolution of a gas took place. This was probably butane.

The Formation of (IV). (i) By Addition of Sodio ethylthioacetoacetate to Ethyl Tetrolate.—Ethyl thioacetoacetate (23 g.) in dry benzene (50 c.c.) was added to emulsified sodium (4.1 g.), suspended in the same solvent (200 c.c.). After allowing the mixture to stand (6 hours) at the room temperature (15°), ethyl tetrolate (20 g.) was added and the whole mass was boiled under reflux (5 hours). It was then treated with ethyl alcohol (40 c.c.) and diluted with excess of hydrochloric acid. From the benzene solution the compound was isolated as an oil, b.p. 155°/12 mm. (Found: C, 55.8; H, 7.1; S, 12.2. $C_{12}H_{18}O_4S$ requires C, 55.8; H, 7.0; S, 12.4 per cent).

(ii) *By the Action of Ethyl β -chlorocrotonate on Sodio ethylthioacetoacetate.*—Ethyl thioacetoacetate (10 g.) was added to a solution of sodium (2 g.) in alcohol (50 c.c.). The mixture was then treated with ethyl β -chlorocrotonate (10 g.) and boiled under reflux (5 hours). The product was diluted with excess of water and extracted with benzene. The fraction, b.p. 158°/15 mm., from the benzene solution was collected. (Found: S, 12.3. $C_{12}H_{18}O_4S$ requires S, 12.4 per cent).

Action of Phenylhydrazine on Compound (IV, R=Me) and the Formation of 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-5-ketodehydro-pyrazolone (III, R=Me).—Ethyl (ethyl β -crotonate)-mercaptocrotonate (IV, 5 g.) was treated with phenylhydrazine (3 g.) and boiled under reflux (1 hour). The product was digested with alcohol and the residue furnished colourless needles of pyrazolone from acetic acid, m.p. 320° (decomp.).

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